

A Feasibility Study With Two Datasets on the Application of the Early Stage HDTO Ontology in Practice

Heritage Digital Twins in Practice: A Finno-Ugric Case Study of Music, Garments, and Architecture

Antal, Dániel

Introduction

This document presents a feasibility study for the *FinFAIR* cascading grant under the *ECHOES / European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)* framework. At the same time, it bridges the findings of *OpenMusE* on data sharing, governance, and metadata repair with the “digital twin” perspective developed within *ECHOES / ECCCH*. The study has two goals: first, to summarise the key technical and governance insights gained in *OpenMusE*; and second, to establish a methodological and semantic bridge toward the next project phase, which will operationalise these methods within the ECCCH by creating *digital twins* of musical works, performances, and architectural heritage.

i Note

This feasibility study was created in withing the framework of the OpenMusE project, and in the preparation of its exploitation pathway under the Stage 2 Echoes proposal writing. We will keep updating this document as we are extending our dataset and gaining more experience with actual, real life data. Please refer to this document as Daniel Antal (2025): *A Feasibility Study With Two Datasets on the Application of the Early Stage HDTO Ontology in Practice* DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17492178
Data Manager: Mester, Anna Márta.

Digital twins are conceived as **composite digital representations** of cultural artefacts or practices—such as a musical work, a performance, or a building—that go beyond a single scanned score, sound recording, or photograph. They integrate multiple perspectives and materials: different arrangements or interpretations of a work, the documents of its first performances, or the architectural plans and subsequent restorations of a building. These digital twins connect tangible and intangible dimensions within one coherent, machine-actionable framework.

Such complexity requires a carefully structured data curation and rights management workflow. In *FinFAIR*, we adopt the concept of a **data sharing space**, following the *Open Music Observatory* model. Instead of forcing contributors into a single metadata schema or legal framework, the data sharing space allows collaboration on an *as-needed* and *as-permitted* basis. Each partner retains control over their own assets while contributing to a common pool of interoperable, ethically governed data. This approach enables the inclusion of a wide variety of materials—free or licensed, public or restricted—without compromising legal compliance or curatorial integrity. Our existing infrastructures, such as the *Open Music Observatory*, the *Slovak Comprehensive Music Database* (<https://hudobnadatabaza.sk/en/>), and the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space* (<https://finnougric.net/>), already demonstrate this approach in practice ¹.

The present feasibility study assesses the applicability of the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* (HDTO) draft on complex digital representations of both material and immaterial heritage. It also provides the conceptual and methodological background for three datasets: *Livonian Music Heritage Digital Twins*, *Finno-Ugric Material Heritage Twins*, and one cross-domain dataset extending the results of *OpenMusE*.

As a synthesis of *OpenMusE* and a pilot for *FinFAIR*, this report provides:

1. A transparent account of how HDTO is operationalised in real-world data environments; and
2. A blueprint for transforming heterogeneous, multilingual heritage datasets into sustainable, semantically linked resources ready for integration into the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage*.

The data curatorial and governance logic of our work, with some technical implementation aspects was presented on *Wikidata Conf 2025*².

Impact Pathways

Our planned *FinFAIR* implementation demonstrates how **small and regionally rooted cultural institutions** can contribute to Europe’s digital transformation on equal terms with large heritage organisations. It provides legal, organisational, semantic, and technical support for connecting the curatorial and collection-management work of national, regional, and village GLAM institutions, community archives, and private collectors. Through this collaboration, digital heritage is no longer confined to isolated catalogues but becomes part of an open, interoperable, and ethically governed ecosystem.

The creation of *Heritage Digital Twins* allows cultural expressions to be represented in their full richness. Songs, stories, artefacts, and performances are linked into composite entities that combine sound, text, image, and context. This structure preserves curatorial depth

¹Our definition here paraphrases (Curry 2020) and the *Data Space for Cultural and Creative Industries* report (EBU and Gaia-X 2022, p16): a “data [sharing] space” is an ecosystem for the exchange, processing, and provision of data between trusted partners. For the *Open Music Observatory*, see (Daniel Antal 2024).

²See references: (Commission et al. 2022; ECHOES Ontology Task Force 2025); conference presentation: (Daniel Antal 2025).

while making heritage data reusable across disciplines. It supports research in ethnomusicology, linguistics, and anthropology, while also giving communities direct access to resources that strengthen local identity and cultural continuity.

Our methodological emphasis on **rights-aware design** ensures that every digital component can be reused safely and ethically. By applying the HDTO and ODRL frameworks, we aim to clarify authors' rights, neighbouring rights, data privacy, and the CARE-based ethical norms surrounding archival recordings, photographs, and transcriptions—materials that have often remained inaccessible because of uncertain licensing. This approach supports a new generation of trustworthy heritage data, enabling both scientific inquiry and community creativity, including language re-learning and participatory cultural revival.

For small ethnolinguistic communities such as the Livonians and Latgalians, the impact of the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space* and the broader *Open Music Observatory* lies in **visibility and participation**. When traditional songs or artefacts become findable and audible online, they invite renewed engagement—singing, learning, and reinterpretation. Through collaboration with Wikimedia Eesti, these digital twins extend into the **Wikimu-seum** environment, where regional museums and citizen curators can co-create multilingual exhibitions without moving physical objects.

By combining open technologies with responsible governance, *FinFAIR* demonstrates how the principles of the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage* can be realised in practice. It links the technical innovation of the digital twin model with social and linguistic sustainability, showing how data infrastructures can support living heritage rather than merely document it.

This feasibility study demonstrates how the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO)* can be practically applied to integrate **tangible** (recordings, notations, instruments) and **intangible** (songs, repertoires, performance traditions) aspects of cultural heritage. By linking these components into a single semantic structure, HDTO enables the reconstruction of cultural meaning that would otherwise remain fragmented across archives, institutions, and languages.

The HDTO approach provides a valuable perspective on the challenges addressed by the *Open Music Europe* project, even though its primary focus is rights management rather than heritage management. HDTO distinguishes between the immaterial cultural object (a musical work) and its *digital twin*—a structured digital representation encompassing digitised scores, textual manifestations, and audio or video recordings. Creating such a composite object and linking it to the immaterial musical work parallels the workflow of rights management agencies that license recordings or scores of a given work. The key difference is that the digital twin requires more explicit and structured rights metadata than traditional heritage documentation. Combining heritage and rights-management data significantly increases the usability and impact of digital heritage: many sound and video recordings held by cultural institutions remain inaccessible precisely because their rights status is unclear or undocumented.

Demonstrator Datasets

The demonstrator datasets were designed to test whether the principles of the **data sharing space** and the **European Interoperability Framework** can be applied to the early-stage *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* (HDTO). Particular attention was given to the legal, organisational, and semantic challenges of constructing digital twins from materials originating in different institutions, collected through distinct curatorial pipelines, and governed by heterogeneous rights, duties, and permissions.

These datasets act as *proofs of concept* showing how distributed heritage materials can be reconnected across linguistic, institutional, and legal boundaries while preserving community authority and ethical integrity.

Livonian Music Heritage Digital Twin Dataset

- **Scope:** Approximately 50 high-context records of Livonian music, with potential parallels from censored or restricted Hungarian recordings, curated according to the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* developed within *ECHOES / ECCCH*.
- **Focus:** Demonstrates a community-centred, decolonising approach to metadata repair that provides *ex post* epistemic justice for displaced, marginalised, or silenced performers. It applies **FAIR** and **CARE** principles to ensure ethical and transparent rights management.
- **Function:** Illustrates how HDTO restores semantic relationships among musical components—melody, lyrics, textual and notated manifestations, and recordings that carry distinct rights layers. It highlights recurring challenges of GDPR and CARE compliance in sound archives, especially where political transitions, institutional closures, or missing provenance data have disrupted legal continuity.
- **Data Sources:**
 - Three collections of the **Archives of Latvian Folklore**,
 - the **Hõimulõimed Finno-Ugric Song Dataset** of 2 025 vocal recordings with lyrics in Livonian, Karelian, Veps, Sámi, Khanti-Mansi, Komi, Mari, Udmurt, Erzyan, Moksha, and Samoyedic languages ³,
 - open databases such as **Discogs** and **MusicBrainz**, and authority control via **Wikidata**, **VIAF**, and **ISNI**.
Public and private sources are connected, including limited-access streaming platforms (e.g. Spotify), demonstrating how licensed and open materials can coexist within one rights-aware infrastructure.
- **Access:** Via <https://finnugric.net> or (Daniel Antal and Mester 2025)

³The **Hõimulõimed Finno-Ugric Song Dataset** was collected by Britt-Kathleen Mere, Bogáta Timár, Agatha Murro, and members of the Hõimulõimed cultural organisation between July 2023 and early 2025. The dataset was subsequently enriched and uploaded into the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space*.

Finno-Ugric Material Heritage Digital Twins Dataset

- **Scope:** Approximately 20 high-context records of Livonian vernacular buildings and associated artefacts curated according to the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* within *ECHOES / ECCCH*.
- **Focus:** Demonstrates community-centred and decolonising metadata practices in documenting tangible heritage. Applies **FAIR** and **CARE** principles to balance open accessibility with local custodianship and cultural sensitivity.
- **Function:** Shows how HDTO reconnects tangible components—a homestead, its constituent buildings, interior structures, and related ethnographic objects—with historical and contemporary photographs. It provides a comparative perspective on modelling tangible versus intangible aspects within a single digital-twin framework.
- **Data Sources:**
 - The **Ethnographic Open-Air Museum of Latvia**,
 - the **Ventspils Museum**, and
 - original photographic documentation collected by the project team.
- **Access:** Via <https://finnougric.net/> or (Daniel Antal, Mester, and Pigozne 2025)

Together, these demonstrators explore how diverse heritage materials—musical and architectural, intangible and tangible—can be curated through a shared ontology and governance model. They validate that *Heritage Digital Twins* can maintain semantic precision, multilingual accessibility, and long-term interoperability while respecting community ownership and ethical data sharing.

Data Sources and Modelling Framework

This section describes the data sources and ontological design principles applied within the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space (FUDSS)*, which forms part of the *Open Music Observatory*. The data come primarily from the Nordic and Baltic regions and from Finno-Ugric ethnolinguistic groups. Together, they serve as the empirical foundation for testing how **tangible** and **intangible** heritage can be represented as interoperable digital twins across community, institutional, and regional boundaries.

Each dataset is semantically aligned to the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO)* classes (`hdt:HC1-HC7`) and properties (`hdt:HP1-HP3`, `dcterms:license`, `prov:wasDerivedFrom`), ensuring consistency with ECCCH ontological standards and long-term interoperability.

Interoperability and Governance

The project builds upon a **decentralised data-sharing-space governance model** developed through the *OpenMusE* Horizon Europe project and extended through collaborations with Wikimedia chapters. This prototype infrastructure already hosts several high-value

datasets used for methodological testing and feasibility analysis, establishing FUDSS as a functioning federated environment.

Initial ingestion activities focused on methodological diversity, testing how a federated community infrastructure could interoperate with **ECCCH**, **Europeana**, **OpenAIRE**, and **DARIAH**⁴. These early datasets remain open for reuse and further ingestion from Finnish, Estonian, and Hungarian national Finno-Ugric collections, as well as from NGOs representing ethnolinguistic communities.

The technical feasibility phase concentrated on **music** as intangible heritage and **dress history** as tangible heritage. It produced a sample dataset and a methodological data paper based on early HDTO drafts. Consultation with domain experts and ontology developers broadened the scope to include built heritage, audiovisual materials, ethnographic artefacts, and still images (photographs, lithographs, prints).

Although *FinFAIR* itself has limited resources for new curation, they are used strategically to produce an HDTO-validated dataset that provides a near-complete representation of Livonian heritage and a comparative dataset for the Latgalian community. Because the Livonian corpus is relatively small, the project aims for exceptionally high coverage—representing at least half of the known material and immaterial heritage of this group. This approach prioritises **depth of modelling and rights clarity** over raw data volume, ensuring that the demonstrators provide meaningful technical feedback to the ECCCH ontology developers.

Open Modelling Questions and Possible HDTO Improvements

Feasibility testing and dataset creation revealed a **structural gap in HDTO v0.1** concerning the relationship between the conceptual digital twin (`HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin`) and its concrete digital components (`HC5-HC8_DigitalRepresentation`).

Because `HC2` is modelled as a subclass of `E89_PropositionalObject` and `HC5-HC8` descend from `crmdig:D1_DigitalObject` (under `E70_Thing`), the two branches are formally disjoint in CIDOC-CRM. The published ontology therefore lacks a direct property connecting a digital twin to its digital surrogates, which can cause accidental mis-ranging when implementers reuse `HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent`.

To address this in practice, the FUDSS introduces a **temporary bridging property**:

Proposed Curatorial Work

Our feasibility study and the creation of a sample dataset demonstrated the advantages of the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* (HDTO) in settings with limited archival depth and fragmented documentation. The digital-twin approach supports not only metadata repair and enrichment but also the decolonisation of cultural records created under unequal historical conditions. For Finno-Ugric and Baltic minorities, documentation is often incomplete, dispersed, or filtered through linguistic and curatorial mediation. Creating digital twins in

⁴For interoperability references, see (Europeana 2017; Manghi et al. 2019; DARIAH-ERIC 2024).

these contexts means reassembling traces of a cultural entity across archives, media types, and languages.

Even within a single institution, elements of a musical work—handwritten scores, printed editions, recordings—are frequently detached from one another. By linking these components into a composite digital-twin object, we follow the logic of the emerging *Records in Contexts* (RiC) model, which represents archival entities as dynamic networks rather than isolated entries. HDTO enables the construction of such semantic relationships, allowing us to represent a work within its historical and linguistic context.

A single example illustrates both the practical and conceptual dimensions of this approach. While analysing a Latvian-language wedding song from Northern Courland, *Šķiraties, rumaties, puķi vedu istabāi*, we located a related variant with mismatched catalogue numbers. Further inspection revealed *Es ar sav' baleliņ*, a phonetic transcription of the same melody recorded by ethnographer Emilis Melngailis in 1930 in Pitragi. As was common at the time, Melngailis transcribed oral materials by ear in Latvian orthography, inconsistently applying diacritics and masking key Livonian phonetic features. Although the original text cannot be fully reconstructed, fragments correspond closely to known Latvian lyrics of the same song.

From this process, we created two digital twins: one for the Latvian-language variant (*Šķiraties, rumaties, puķi vedu istabāi*) and another for the Livonian version (*Es ar sav' baleliņ*). Each carries its own linguistic and cultural context yet remains semantically linked to the other as a probable variant of the same musical work. This approach allows them to coexist as culturally distinct but interconnected heritage entities, avoiding ethnic essentialism by situating the song within shared Latvian, Livonian, and Finno-Ugric traditions.

The example also reflects the layered colonial histories that shaped these data. Northern Courland passed through Russian, German, and Soviet rule, while the Livonians—a small Finno-Ugric minority—were largely assimilated by the early twentieth century. Their heritage was mostly documented by external ethnographers from Latvia, Finland, Estonia, and Hungary, whose transcriptions and classifications often obscured linguistic features and local meanings.

To make such collections meaningful for contemporary Livonian speakers and researchers, it is necessary to reconstruct not only the metadata but also the epistemic conditions under which they were produced. The digital-twin approach enables this reconstruction by linking dispersed records across languages, archives, and political regimes into shared semantic structures. Within this framework, HDTO provides a means of representing heritage that acknowledges multilingualism, displacement, and asymmetrical authorship while restoring interpretative authority to the communities themselves.

Implementation

Why Wikibase as an Architectural Choice

Wikibase provides an effective bridge between curatorial workflows and semantic-web modelling. As an open, collaborative database, it allows curators and researchers to describe heritage materials in a human-readable form while keeping data machine-actionable through RDF export. This duality makes it ideal for projects balancing community participation, multilingual metadata, and interoperability with formal ontologies such as HDTO, CIDOC-CRM, or schema.org.

In contexts of limited archival depth and dispersed or diasporic heritage, strict ontology modelling can be too rigid for practical curation. Wikibase supports incremental enrichment: incomplete or conflicting data can coexist with qualified statements, references, and provenance notes, allowing curators to capture uncertainty without breaking semantic consistency. Its flexible data model permits the gradual introduction of domain ontologies—digital-twin classes, heritage-entity relations, and component hierarchies—without disrupting existing documentation.

Architecturally, Wikibase serves as a **bridging layer** between descriptive archives and semantic infrastructures. It connects traditional cataloguing and fieldwork metadata with graph-based reasoning, while federated queries and reconciliation features enable linkage across institutions and languages. Within the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space*, this approach allows complex, multilingual, and historically layered heritage to be represented transparently and sustainably: human curators maintain an accessible knowledge base, while automated exports produce HDTO-compliant datasets for long-term interoperability.

Wikibase has proven effective for multilingual authority control (Bianchini, Bargioni, and Pellizzari di San Girolamo 2021; Fagervig 2023). The Finnish Wikibase pilot of the National Library of Finland demonstrated how it can connect museum, linguistic, and archival records while supporting community participation (National Library of Finland 2021). Similar experiences in minority-language contexts—such as the Võro User Group (Wikimedians of Võro language User Group 2025) and Wikimedia Norge’s Sámi knowledge project (Wikimedia Norge 2020)—show that Wikibase can combine semantic interoperability with respect for knowledge sovereignty and multilingual representation. These precedents confirm that Wikibase can act as a shared curatorial platform for minority and diasporic heritage without imposing a single institutional metadata regime.

By aligning the Wikibase data model with the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology* (HDTO), curated materials in our knowledge graph can be exported directly into the semantic infrastructure of the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage* (ECCCH). This export layer transforms each composite Wikibase record into a structured HDTO dataset, linking it to wider European data spaces through persistent identifiers, multilingual vocabularies, and standardised provenance. In this way, Wikibase functions not only as a curatorial interface but also as an enabling architecture for open, interoperable cultural-heritage data within the evolving European research ecosystem.

Data Model Implementation

Our knowledge graph represents cultural-heritage entities and their digital counterparts according to the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO)* used by the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)*.

In HDTO v0.1, the class `HC1_HeritageEntity` denotes any real-world object—tangible or intangible—valued for its cultural, social, or scientific significance. It is a subclass of `crm:E70_Thing` and covers physical, immaterial, or born-digital heritage recognised as having enduring importance. Individual events are not `HC1` instances but may be associated through event types or patterns.

Each real-world heritage entity—for instance, a song, manuscript, or artefact—is represented as an instance of `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity`. These entities are not stored directly in Wikibase but generated dynamically during export to an HDTO-compliant dataset.

Digital twins and their heritage entities are linked through `hdt:HP1_hasDigitalTwin` (inverse `hdt:HP1i_isDigitalTwinOf`), which asserts that a digital object documents a real-world entity.

Within each composite twin we distinguish between

- the **main digital twin** (the Wikibase item itself), and
- its **digital components**, corresponding to individual files or modalities such as lyrics, audio, images, or scores.

Material Assets

The *Dēliņi Homestead*, constructed between 1819 and the early twentieth century, forms a distinctive three-courtyard layout ([fudss:Q5582](#)). Originally located in Lūžņa on the Livonian coast, it was relocated to the Latvian Ethnographic Open-Air Museum in 1971.

```
:Delini_Homestead a `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi Homestead"@en ;
  `hdt:HP15_isHeritageOf` :Livonian_Community .
```

A combined barn-shed built around 1870 is modelled as a `hdt:HC3_TangibleAspect` of the homestead.

```
:Delini_BarnShed a `hdt:HC3_TangibleAspect` ;
  `crm:P46_is_composed_of` :Delini_Ramp ;
  `hdt:HP1_hasDigitalTwin` :Delini_BarnShed_Twin .
```

Three photographs document the barn-shed; each image is a separate creative work with its own licence.

```

:fudss:Q5579 a `hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject` ;
  rdfs:label "Barn-shed, rear view with ramp"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Delini_Ramp ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> .

:fudss:Q5580 a `hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject` ;
  rdfs:label "Barn-shed, courtyard view"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Delini_BarnShed ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/> .

:fudss:Q5581 a `hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject` ;
  rdfs:label "Barn interior"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Delini_BarnShed ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/> .

```

The digital twin for the homestead, *Delini_Homestead_Twin*, is an `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` aggregating all documentation.

It is published as `fudss:Q5582` (TTL: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q5582.ttl>).

The digital twin for the homestead, *Delini_Homestead_Twin*, is an `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` aggregating all documentation.

It is a subclass of `crm:E89_PropositionalObject` and represents a curated body of digital information about the `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` — the *Dēliņi Homestead* itself. In our system this digital twin is published as `fudss:Q5582` (TTL: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q5582.ttl>).

```

:Delini_Homestead_Twin a `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi Homestead (digital twin)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent` :fudss:Q5579 , :fudss:Q5580 , :fudss:Q5581 ;
  `dcterms:description` "Composite digital twin containing
  photographs under mixed Creative Commons licences."@en .

```

Physical domain	Digital domain
HC1 = <i>Dēliņi Homestead</i>	HC2 = Curated digital twin
HC3 = Buildings / elements	HC7 = Photographs / blueprints (licences vary)

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Immaterial Assets

The folk song *Tšitšõrlinki*, *tšitšõrlinki* ([fudss:Q4168](#)) represents Livonian intangible heritage—an anonymous vocal composition preserved through oral tradition and documented by Hilda Grīva.

```
:Tsitsorlinki_Song a `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` ;
  rdfs:label "Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki"@lv ;
  `hdt:HP15_isHeritageOf` :Livonian_Community .
```

The melodic and textual form of the song is an `hdt:HC4_IntangibleAspect`:

```
:Tsitsorlinki_IntangibleAspect a `hdt:HC4_IntangibleAspect` ;
  `hdt:HP6_hasManifestationEvent` :Tsitsorlinki_Performance_1962 ;
  `hdt:HP1_hasDigitalTwin` :Tsitsorlinki_Twin .
```

Several documents and recordings represent this song—each with its own licence: a hand-written score, a printed sheet, a text file, an archival sound recording, and a commercial Spotify release.

```
:Tsitsorlinki_HandwrittenScore a `hdt:HC6_DigitalDocument` ;
  rdfs:label "Hand-written score of 'Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki'"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/> .
```

```
:Tsitsorlinki_PrintedSheet a `hdt:HC6_DigitalDocument` ;
  rdfs:label "Printed score of 'Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki'"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> .
```

```
:Tsitsorlinki_LyricsText a `hdt:HC6_DigitalDocument` ;
  rdfs:label "Lyrics text of 'Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki'"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:format` "text/plain" .
```

```
:Tsitsorlinki_ArchivalRecording a `hdt:HC5_DigitalRepresentation` ;
  rdfs:label "Archival recording of 'Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki'"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/> .
```

```
:Tsitsorlinki_CommercialRecording a `hdt:HC5_DigitalRepresentation` ;
  rdfs:label "Commercial recording of 'Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki'"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> .
```

The digital twin *Tsitsorlinki_Twin* aggregates these representations as an `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin`, encapsulating a curated body of digital information about the song and its manifestations. All components are linked via `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent` (inverse `hdt:HP3i_isDigitalTwinComponent`). To express modality-specific links, FinFAIR defines sub-properties of `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent`:

Modality	Sub-property	Inverse	Usage
Visual representation	<code>fudss:hasDepiction</code>	<code>fudss:isDepictionOf</code>	Images / video
Audio recording	<code>fudss:hasRecording</code>	<code>fudss:isRecordingOf</code>	Sound files
Musical score	<code>fudss:hasScore</code>	<code>fudss:isScoreOf</code>	Notation / sheet music
Textual edition	<code>fudss:hasManifestation</code>	<code>fudss:isManifestationOf</code>	PDFs / text
Mixed / unspecified	<code>hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent</code>	<code>hdt:HP3i_isDigitalTwinComponent</code>	Generic use of all

This sub-property pattern ensures that multimodal components remain semantically precise while fully compliant with the HDTO framework.

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Examples

The following example combines a *material* and an *immaterial* heritage entity, showing how both can be modelled within the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO) and exported to the Europeana Data Model (EDM) without loss of information.

Each entity follows the same logic: an `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` linked to an `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin`, which aggregates individual digital components (`hdt:HC5-HC7`).

Every component carries its own `dcterms:license` statement, ensuring that the rights for reuse and access remain explicit and unambiguous.

Example A – Material heritage: the Dēliņi combined barn-shed

The *Dēliņi combined barn-shed* is a physical building, part of the Dēliņi homestead ensemble relocated to the Latvian Ethnographic Open-Air Museum. It has a single photographic documentation available on Wikimedia Commons and a thumbnail hosted on Reprerbase. This is a one-to-one mapping between a cultural-heritage object and its digital representation.

```
:Delini_BarnShed a `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi combined barn-shed"@lv ;
  `hdt:HP15_isHeritageOf` :Livonian_Community ;
  `hdt:HP1_hasDigitalTwin` :Delini_BarnShed_Twin .
```

```

:Delini_BarnShed_Twin a `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi combined barn-shed (digital twin)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent` :Delini_BarnShed_Photo ,
                                     :Delini_BarnShed_Thumbnail ;
  `dcterms:description` "Digital twin containing a high-resolution photograph and a thumb

:Delini_BarnShed_Photo a `hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi combined barn-shed, front view (photo)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Delini_BarnShed ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> ;
  `edm:isShownBy` <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Dēliņi_combined_barn-shed_(ph
  `edm:rights` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> .

:Delini_BarnShed_Thumbnail a `hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject` ;
  rdfs:label "Dēliņi combined barn-shed, thumbnail (photo)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Delini_BarnShed ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> ;
  `edm:hasView` <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/images/thumb/FUDSS-Q5578.jpg/600px-FUDSS-Q5578
  `edm:rights` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> .

```

Example B – Immaterial heritage: the Livonian folk song “Tšitšōrlinki, tšitšōrlinki”

The *Tšitšōrlinki*, *tšitšōrlinki* folk song is an item of intangible Livonian cultural heritage, traditionally performed by members of the Livonian community.

Its digital twin contains two distinct audio components: one archival recording preserved in the Latvian Folklore Archives (non-commercial, research use) and one commercial streaming release distributed by **ALOADED** (Spotify).

Both components refer to the same performance but carry different rights and access conditions.

```

:Tsitsorlinki_Song a `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` ;
  rdfs:label "Tšitšōrlinki, tšitšōrlinki"@lv ;
  `hdt:HP15_isHeritageOf` :Livonian_Community ;
  `hdt:HP1_hasDigitalTwin` :Tsitsorlinki_Twin .

:Tsitsorlinki_Twin a `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` ;
  rdfs:label "Tšitšōrlinki, tšitšōrlinki (digital twin)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent` :Tsitsorlinki_ArchivalRecording ,
                                     :Tsitsorlinki_SpotifyRelease ;
  `dcterms:description` "Digital twin aggregating archival and commercial releases of th

# Component 1 - Archival recording (research, non-commercial)
:Tsitsorlinki_ArchivalRecording a `hdt:HC5_DigitalRepresentation` ;
  rdfs:label "Archival recording (Latvian Folklore Archives)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;

```

```

`dcterms:license` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/> ;
`dcterms:accessRights` "restricted; research only"@en ;
`dcterms:rightsHolder` :Latvian_Folklore_Archives ;
`dcterms:provenance` "Recorded during ethnographic fieldwork; access under non-commercial license"@en ;
`edm:isShownBy` <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/media/Q4169.wav> ;
`edm:rights` <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/> .

# Component 2 - Commercial release (Spotify stream)
:Tsitsorlinki_SpotifyRelease a `hdt:HC5_DigitalRepresentation` ;
  rdfs:label "Commercial release (Spotify stream)"@en ;
  `hdt:HP22_represents` :Tsitsorlinki_Song ;
  `dcterms:creator` :Performer_KristinKrassone_Pub ;
  `cc:attributionName` "Katrīne Krassone" ;
  `dcterms:license` <https://spotify.com/legal/end-user-agreement> ;
  `dcterms:rightsHolder` :Producer_ALOADED ;
  `dcterms:accessRights` "streaming only"@en ;
  `edm:hasView` <https://open.spotify.com/track/xyz> ;
  `edm:rights` <https://spotify.com/legal/end-user-agreement> .

# Contextual entities
:Latvian_Folklore_Archives a `edm:Agent` ;
  rdfs:label "Digital Archives of Latvian Folklore"@en .

:Producer_ALOADED a `edm:Agent` ;
  rdfs:label "ALOADED (Label and Distributor)"@en .

:Performer_KristinKrassone_Pub a `edm:Agent` ;
  rdfs:label "Katrīne Krassone"@en ;
  `cc:attributionName` "Katrīne Krassone" ;
  `skos:note` "Performer consented to public attribution for the Spotify release."@en .

```

The digital twin *Tsitsorlinki_Twin* aggregates these representations as an `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin`, encapsulating a curated body of digital information about the song and its manifestations. All components are linked via `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent` (inverse `hdt:HP3i_isDigitalTwinComponent`).

To express modality-specific links, FinFAIR defines sub-properties of `hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent`:

Modality	Sub-property	Inverse	Usage
Visual representation	<code>fudss:hasDepiction</code>	<code>fudss:isDepictionOf</code>	Images / video
Audio recording	<code>fudss:hasRecording</code>	<code>fudss:isRecordingOf</code>	Sound files
Musical score	<code>fudss:hasScore</code>	<code>fudss:isScoreOf</code>	Notation / sheet music
Textual edition	<code>fudss:hasManifestation</code>	<code>fudss:isManifestationOf</code>	PDFs / text
Mixed / unspecified	<code>hdt:HP3_hasDigitalTwinComponent</code>	<code>hdt:HP3i_isDigitalTwinComponent</code>	General use

This sub-property pattern ensures that multimodal components remain semantically precise while fully compliant with the HDTO framework.

Combined Examples

The two demonstrators—a **material** object (the *Dēliņi barn-shed*) and an **immaterial** object (the *Tšitšōrlinki* song)—illustrate how both domains can be modelled within HDTO and exported to the **Europeana Data Model (EDM)** without loss of information. Each entity follows the same structure: an `HC1_HeritageEntity` linked to an `HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin`, which aggregates `HC5-HC7` digital components. Every component carries its own `dcterms:license`, making rights and reuse conditions explicit.

Heritage entity	Digital twin components	Rights model
<i>Dēliņi barn-shed</i> (HC1)	Photograph, thumbnail (HC7)	CC BY 4.0
<i>Tšitšōrlinki, tšitšōrlinki</i> (HC1)	Archival WAV, Spotify stream (HC5)	CC BY-NC 4.0 / Spotify EULA

This unified structure shows how HDTO accommodates both tangible and intangible heritage while remaining interoperable with EDM. Each digital file retains an explicit licence, enabling transparent and FAIR access across public, research, and educational contexts.

Data Semantics, Thesauri, and Authority Integration

The HDTO implementation in FinFAIR depends not only on internal ontology design but also on the careful integration of existing authority files and controlled vocabularies. Because our datasets integrate materials from archives, museums, and community collections across four language areas—Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, and Hungarian—we must ensure semantic consistency while preserving linguistic and curatorial diversity.

Use of Controlled Vocabularies and Thesauri

In the peer-reviewed discussion of our FUDSS prototype (Dániel Antal et al. 2025), we evaluated the usability of major thesauri such as the *Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus®* (AAT) and the *Library of Congress Subject Headings* (LCSH), the latter widely adopted by national music libraries. These vocabularies have decades of use but were originally designed for U.S. institutions. The AAT has since evolved through multilingual collaborations (Harpring et al. 2020), including a Portuguese localisation (Silva 2022).

The main advantage of AAT and LCSH is global familiarity; their limitation is scale and origin—comprehensive adoption for new regional collections is often a multi-year process. For example, most of our digital surrogates come from Estonia’s *muus.ee* system, which uses

an Estonian-only thesaurus. Building full mappings between AAT and *muus.ee* would itself constitute a large, independent project.

Our approach combines Wikidata’s pragmatic “good-enough” mapping with the *eXtreme Design* methodology used in the Polifonia ontology family (Blomqvist, Hammar, and Pre-sutti 2016; Berardinis et al. 2023). This method reuses semantic fragments to address explicit *competency questions*—for example, how to represent garment types or musical forms—without needing to localise entire thesauri. We follow AAT’s localisation guidelines only in narrow areas where we have sufficient searchable objects and digital twins.

Most Latgalian and Livonian garment collections, for instance, date from the late nineteenth century. We therefore harmonised only the vocabulary for that period’s peasant dress across Estonian, Finnish, Latvian, and AAT schemas. AAT’s upper-level structure (“shirt”, “upper-body garment”) serves as a scaffold for culturally specific subclasses such as *kitasnik* (dress) and *kuhiksõlg* (Seto conical brooch). Although AAT does not yet cover all Finno-Ugric material culture, it provides a workable structure for cross-institutional alignment and diasporic item discovery.

Where AAT coverage is insufficient—especially for intangible heritage like music genres or ritual practices—we extend alignment through **Wikidata property sets** and **local SKOS concept schemes** within the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space (FUDSS)*.

For linguistic and cultural concepts unique to small Finno-Ugric communities, we apply **OntoLex-Lemon** to build lexeme-based thesauri capturing variant spellings, etymologies, and semantic overlaps among related languages (Livonian, Võro, Seto, Mari). Each lexical entry is mapped to AAT or Wikidata equivalents (`skos:exactMatch`, `skos:closeMatch`, `skos:broadMatch`) to enable multilingual query expansion and culturally specific representation.

Spatial data pose similar challenges, as historical sources often use multilingual or obsolete place names.

Geographical Namespaces and Spatial Authorities

Place names are a major source of inconsistency across archival sources. Historical materials often employ outdated or colonial-era terminology, while modern boundaries differ substantially. FinFAIR addresses this through a **dual-namespaces model**:

- **Contemporary entities:** normalised via **GeoNames** and **Wikidata** geospatial ontologies.
- **Historical entities:** preserved as custom SKOS concepts or FUDSS-local authorities derived from archival inventories.

We built a multilingual reconciliation layer—a *gazetteer*—linking historical and modern names (e.g. *Petseri*, *Pechory*, *Petschur*) under canonical identifiers. Beyond standard geocoding, our approach integrates multi-script, multi-ethnic, and historical variants verified by Finno-Ugric scholars.

The Livonian coast serves as our prototype. Using the *Livonian Place Name Catalogue* (Ernštreits 2020; Ernštreits, Šuvcāne, and Damberg 2024), we compiled names across Livonian, Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, Russian, and Baltic German. This multilingual layering improved recall of heritage materials in foreign or colonial catalogues. Even within a dozen villages, orthographic variation is vast—e.g. *Irē* (Livonian) vs. *Irben* or *Gross-Irben* (German). Soviet-era catalogues standardised Latvian forms; imperial sources retained German exonyms. These linguistic and political layers illustrate why rigid top-down normalisation is impractical.

We therefore published a prototype gazetteer linking (Ernštreits 2020; Ernštreits, Šuvcāne, and Damberg 2024; Daniel Antal, Pigozne, and Mester 2025) to multilingual identifiers. It connects surface forms of Livonian, Estonian, Russian, and German with standardised Livonian and Latvian names. This enabled the discovery of Livonian garments in Finnish and Estonian collections previously unknown to Latvian researchers.

Each location node stores both current and historical identifiers, allowing queries by modern coordinates or original ethnographic appellations. For example, “Kolka” (modern Latvian) and “Kūolka” (Livonian) are distinct labels of the same entity—preserving linguistic distinction while maintaining referential unity.

Authority Files for Persons, Organisations, and Works

Authority control ensures continuity between FinFAIR datasets and the wider European infrastructure. It links people, institutions, and works across repositories, enabling both automated interoperability and human validation.

- **Persons:** aligned through **VIAF**, **ISNI**, and **Wikidata**; when absent, internal IDs with open crosswalks.
- **Institutions:** identified via **ROR** and **Wikidata**, ensuring compatibility with **OpenAIRE** and **EOSC**.
- **Works:** linked to **MusicBrainz**, **Wikidata**, **GLAM Wiki Works**, or national library records.
- **Sound recordings:** identified by **ISRC** and, where accessible, platform identifiers (Spotify, Deezer, YouTube), ensuring discoverability and lawful reuse.

Ontological Alignment

HDTO functions as the central semantic layer, extended and cross-referenced with established ontologies:

Domain	Ontology / Schema	Purpose
Tangible heritage	CIDOC-CRM 7.3	Provenance, physical description
Archival context	Records in Context (RiC-O)	Archival hierarchy and ISAD(G) compatibility
Bibliographic data	DCTERMS, BIBFRAME	Publication and citation
Music and sound	DDEX, Polifonia Ontologies	Rights, instrumentation, performer roles
Language and lexicon	OntoLex-Lemon	Linguistic data and lexical thesauri
Rights management	ODRL	Structured rights policies for digital components

Mappings between these ontologies are defined through `owl:equivalentClass` and `owl:equivalentProperty` within the FUDSS namespace. This ensures that exported datasets merge seamlessly with **ECCCH** and **Europeana** ingestion pipelines.

Because of our architecture, HDTO operates both within the *Wikibase Data Model* and as a formal ontology. As HDTO derives from **CIDOC-CRM**, already mapped to Wikibase (Wikimedia Foundation 2025; Pfeiffer and Gayo 2021; Kesäniemi, Koho, and Hyvönen 2022), we successfully aligned version 0.1 to produce a demonstration dataset.

Following the pragmatic logic applied to vocabularies, we do not aim to map **DCTERMS**, **RiC-O**, or **CIDOC-CRM** in their entirety. Instead, using *eXtreme Design*, we formulate competency questions tailored to our institutional data sources—those in **FinFAIR** and the Finnish, Estonian, and Hungarian repositories—to ensure interoperability across bibliographic, archival, and museum records.

Our alignment extends to **DDEX**, the music-industry metadata standard. Aware of metadata bias and “ontological hijacking,” our mapping remains minimal and principled: ensuring coherence between title and name headings (for works and recordings) and between time and place appellations used in CIDOC-derived systems and music data sources. The feasibility dataset confirms this high-level interoperability in practice.

Multilingual Data Representation

All human-readable labels (`rdfs:label`, `skos:prefLabel`) are provided in at least two languages: English and the original language of the source (Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, or minority languages such as Livonian or Võro). Transliterations follow ISO 9:1995 and established national orthographic standards for non-Latin scripts. This ensures

that ECCCH harvesters can retrieve English-language metadata for interoperability, while community users can query and display data in their native scripts.

Multilingual representation is not only a usability feature but a core part of FinFAIR’s ethical and epistemic framework. It recognises linguistic diversity as a form of intangible heritage and ensures that endangered or minority languages remain visible in digital infrastructures. Every dataset therefore carries both internationally legible and locally meaningful identifiers, balancing machine readability with cultural specificity.

At a later stage, we plan to introduce explicit lexicographical modelling through the Lexeme extension of Wikidata and Wikibase, which implements the OntoLex-Lemon ontology. This will allow the project to represent linguistic variation, etymology, and dialectal features more precisely and to interlink cultural-heritage data with emerging *European Language Data Space* resources.

Rights Management

Rights management within the FinFAIR framework is designed to be **transparent, interoperable, and machine-readable**.

It combines the Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO) with practical extensions in Wikibase that allow curators to express not only licences but also contextual usage rules derived from the *Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)*.

While large digital-heritage platforms such as Europeana or DARIAH rely mainly on single-URI licence models (`edm:rights`, `dcterms:license`), FinFAIR adds an optional layer of structured **use policies** to handle complex, multimodal works such as music or film, where overlapping rights coexist.

Personal Data and GDPR

Every `hdt:HC1_HeritageEntity` or `hdt:HC2_HeritageDigitalTwin` may link to living agents—performers, collectors, researchers, donors, or other data subjects—through `dcterms:creator`, `prov:wasAttributedTo`, or `crm:P14_carried_out_by`.

Under the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, these names constitute *personal data*.

Before publication or linkage, consent and attribution are evaluated:

- **Attribution** — if the person consents to credit, we use `cc:attributionName`.
- **Pseudonymisation** — if consent is uncertain, we use neutral labels, e.g. “Field recording performer, 1962”.
- **Anonymity** — if the person requests privacy, all identifying information is withheld.
- The selected attribution mode determines the applicable licence. For example, CC-BY assumes credit, while pseudonymised or anonymous materials default to CC0, BY-NC, or a corresponding `rightsstatements.org` URI.

For older archival materials, FinFAIR follows Europeana’s approach: if the data subjects are certainly deceased (typically pre-1925), personal-data restrictions no longer apply.

Simple Case: One Licence per File

For non-composite objects—photographs, scans, or plain-text documents—the **Europeana Data Model (EDM)** `edm:rights` field provides sufficient legal clarity. FinFAIR implements this directly via the Wikibase property `use rights`, which corresponds to `dcterms:license` and `edm:rights`.

Every Image Has a Story — and a Legal One

From creation to licence to expiry, each event rewrites its rights.

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Even these “simple” cases are dynamic. A copyright protection term may expire, making a less accessible item fully reusable under the public domain. Rightsholders may change their minds, and give a more permissive license, for example, change from CC BY-NC-ND to CC-BY-SA, allowing commercial use and derivate works.

Type of object	HDTO class	Typical examples
Digital text	<code>hdt:HC6_DigitalDocument</code>	metadata exports, lyrics, PDFs
Digital image	<code>hdt:HC7_DigitalVisualObject</code>	photographs, scans, blueprints
Simple audio file	<code>hdt:HC5_DigitalRepresentation</code>	single or ambiguous recordings

Each digital component carries: - `use rights` → a URI pointing to a standard licence (e.g. CC-BY, CC0);

- optional provenance (`dcterms:rightsHolder`, `dcterms:accessRights`, `dcterms:provenance`).

The composite digital twin (HC2) aggregates multiple components but does not override their licences.

When reused, the **most restrictive** licence among components applies.

Wikibase Rights Extensions

To align HDTO, EDM, and Wikibase, FinFAIR defines two complementary properties and one supporting class.

Property: use rights (wd:P486)

Field	Description
Label	use rights
Description	Links a digital object to a URI identifying the applicable licence or rights statement (e.g. rightsstatements.org, Creative Commons).
Aliases	licence; rights; edm:rights; demi:license; datacite:rights
Datatype	External identifier (URI)
Equivalent properties	dcterms:license, edm:rights, datacite:rights
Full definition	https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/P486.ttl

Example:

- [Dēliņi homestead detail: combined barn-shed \(detail photo\)](#)
use rights: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/deed.en>
- [The Livonian Community House in Mazirbe \(photograph\)](#)
use rights: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>

This property provides one-to-one interoperability with both Europeana and research repositories using DataCite

Property: use policy (wd:P487)

Field	Description
Label	use policy
Description	Links a digital object to a <i>local</i> rights or usage policy item within the same Wikibase instance (e.g. “Listen on Spotify”). Used when the applicable terms are described internally rather than via an external URI.

Field	Description
Aliases	has policy; user rights policy
Datatype	Wikibase item
(Near) Equivalent class	odrl:Policy
Full definition	https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/P487.ttl

Class: use policy (wd:Q5606)

Field	Description
Label	use policy
Description	A simplified representation of <code>odrl:Policy</code> within Wikibase. Describes how a digital object may be accessed, used, or shared under specific conditions. Instances act as human-readable policy nodes.
Full definition	https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q5606.ttl

Example instance of this class:

[Q5608 - Listen on Spotify](#)

You may listen to this recording via the Spotify web or mobile player, either for free or with a subscription, under Spotify's End-User Licence.

This simplified approach to ODRL was first introduced in our *WikidataCon 2025* presentation, where we demonstrated how Wikibase can represent policy semantics (“play”, “reproduce”, “not download”) without external RDF frameworks.

Complex Case: Composite Rights

Multimodal cultural objects, such as sound recordings, often involve overlapping rights: composer, lyricist, performer, producer, and distributor.

In such cases, each digital representation (HC5) carries its own `use rights` and `use policy`.

One Song, Two Paths of Use

Different licences govern what you can copy — and what you can play.


```
# --- Commercially released song -----
wd:Q4745 a wikibase:Item ;
  rdfs:label "Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki (commercial release)"@en ;
  schema:description "Commercially released version of the traditional Livonian folk song, performed by Hilda Griva."@en ;
  p:P410 s:Q4745-spotify-access . # access point → Spotify link (statement node)

# --- Statement node for the access point -----
s:Q4745-spotify-access a wikibase:Statement ;
  ps:P410 <https://open.spotify.com/track/123456789abcdef> ;
  # Spotify player URL
  pq:P483 wd:Q5989 . # qualifier: has policy → Listen on Spotify

# --- The policy item -----
wd:Q5989 a wb:UsePolicy ;
  rdfs:label "Listen on Spotify"@en ;
  schema:description "You may listen to this recording via the Spotify web or mobile player, free or by subscription, according to Spotify's End User License."@en ;
  dct:license <https://www.spotify.com/legal/end-user-agreement/> .
```

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Example: *Tšitšõrlinki, tšitšõrlinki*

- **Archival recording** — accessible under CC-BY-NC, for non-commercial research. use policy: “Non-commercial analysis and reproduction permitted.”
- **Spotify release** — available for streaming only under Spotify’s end-user licence. use policy: “Listen on Spotify.”

These are linked within a single digital twin (HC2), which aggregates but does not merge or override rights.

Broad Interoperability: From Archive To Spotify

Our data model supports only “patterns” of important standard library, archive, museum, rights management conceptual models; functionality is not optimised for libraries but for cross-institutional use

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Aggregators such as Europeana can display the most restrictive licence, while research or educational users can act according to the specified use policy.

Summary

1. **GDPR compliance** — screen linked agents, pseudonymise or anonymise where required.
2. **Simple case** — one use rights URI per file, equivalent to `edm:rights`.
3. **Composite case** — multiple components, each with its own use rights and use policy.
4. **Interoperability** — full equivalence with EDM, DCTERMS, and ODRL.
5. **Scalability** — lightweight for images and texts, yet expressive for music and audio-visual works.

This model provides a sustainable bridge between **cultural heritage and research data ecosystems**, ensuring that digital twins can circulate legally and ethically within the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage.

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